

Developing a national digital platform for detecting potentially inappropriate medications: adaptation of the EU(7)-PIM list to Bulgarian healthcare practice

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Abstract

Objective: Population aging in Europe, particularly in Bulgaria, where adults ≥ 65 years represent 24% of the population, increases risks related to multimorbidity, polypharmacy, potentially inappropriate prescribing (PIP), and potentially inappropriate medications (PIM). This study aimed to adapt the EU(7)-PIM List for the national context, assess national market availability of listed substances, and develop a comprehensive technical framework for digital integration.

Materials and methods: A three-stage methodological approach was applied: (1) Bulgarian translation and expert validation of the EU(7)-PIM List; (2) verification of authorization and market availability of all included international nonproprietary names (INNs) using the Bulgarian Drug Agency (BDA) and National Council on Prices and Reimbursement (NCPR) databases; and (3) development of technical specifications for digitalization and interoperability with NCPR registries.

Results: Of 277 INNs, 138 (49.8%) were available on the Bulgarian market. A comprehensive digital framework was designed.

Conclusion: This study provides the first methodological and technical basis for a nationally integrated PIM identification system in Bulgaria, supporting safer pharmacotherapy in older adults.

Keywords

Digital PIM platform, EU(7)-PIM List, older adults, polypharmacy, potentially inappropriate medications (PIMs)

Introduction

The aging of the European population constitutes a significant challenge for public health systems. Recent Eurostat statistics indicate that individuals aged 65 years and older comprise 21.6% of the European Union's population (Eurostat 2025), whereas in Bulgaria, this proportion is

even higher at 24% (NSI 2024). Such demographic trends necessitate the development of efficient and targeted healthcare strategies, particularly for the management of multimorbidity and polypharmacy among older adults. Polypharmacy, typically defined as the concurrent use of five or more medications, has become increasingly common in this demographic and is associated with a range

of adverse outcomes, including elevated risks of mortality, falls, hospitalizations, adverse drug reactions (ADRs), drug–drug interactions, and medication nonadherence, all of which contribute to rising healthcare expenditures (Maher et al. 2014). Recent data from 27 European countries and Israel show that polypharmacy affects approximately 36.2% of adults aged 65 and over, with prevalence varying widely by country and closely linked to multiple sociodemographic, health, and functional factors (Bonanno et al. 2025). Additionally, a systematic review conducted across Central and Eastern Europe reported that the prevalence of potentially inappropriate prescribing among older adults ranged from 6.5% to 95.8%, with a median of 34.6% and an interquartile range of 25.9–63.2%, highlighting substantial variability between countries and care settings and underscoring the need for improved prescribing quality and harmonized assessment tools in the region (Brkic et al. 2022a, b). Given that polypharmacy is one of the strongest predictors of potentially inappropriate prescribing (PIP) and increases the likelihood of exposure to potentially inappropriate medications (PIMs), addressing inappropriate prescribing has become a central priority in geriatric pharmacotherapy. To mitigate these risks, various instruments and methodologies have been developed to identify PIMs. These include explicit criteria, such as clearly defined lists developed through consensus or guidelines, and implicit criteria, which rely on clinical judgment. Among the most widely adopted tools are the explicit Beers Criteria (USA), STOPP/START Criteria (Ireland), and the EU(7)-PIM List, the latter developed through multinational consensus across seven European Union member states. Implicit assessment tools, such as the Medication Appropriateness Index and the Lipton criteria, offer additional clinical flexibility.

Across Europe, the adoption and adaptation of these tools is heterogeneous. Western European countries, including Germany, Ireland, and France, have developed or customized their own national PIM lists (Laroche et al. 2007; Wohlgemuth et al. 2024; Doherty et al. 2025). In contrast, Central and Eastern European countries have increasingly moved toward integrating established tools into their national healthcare frameworks (Renom-Guiteras et al. 2015; Pazan et al. 2018).

Several studies have underscored the importance of developing or adapting national PIM lists to accurately reflect local prescribing practices, drug availability, and healthcare system characteristics (Fernández et al. 2025). Evidence indicates that the applicability of international tools may be constrained when certain medications or formulations are unavailable or differ across markets. Consequently, national adaptations are crucial to ensure the clinical relevance, validity, and utility of PIM assessment tools in routine practice (Lisowska et al. 2022). In this context, the decision to adapt the EU(7)-PIM List for Bulgaria was informed by both scientific and pragmatic considerations. The EU(7)-PIM List was established through a rigorous, consensus-driven Delphi process that engaged experts from seven European Union member states—Germany, Estonia, Finland, France, the Netherlands, Spain, and the

Czech Republic—thereby ensuring broad representativeness and methodological rigor. Its comprehensive scope, multinational consensus, and explicit criteria render it particularly suitable for adaptation by countries aiming to harmonize with European prescribing standards.

This article outlines the steps undertaken to adapt and implement the EU(7)-PIM List within the context of Bulgarian clinical practice, as well as the measures taken to digitalize the list to facilitate its integration into national healthcare systems and support clinical decision-making.

Materials and methods

This methodological study was conducted with the objective of adapting the EU(7)-PIM List to the Bulgarian healthcare context and developing a digital, interoperable version suitable for integration with national regulatory databases. The adaptation process comprised three main stages:

1. Translation of the EU(7)-PIM List

The original EU(7)-PIM List (Renom-Guiteras et al. 2015) was translated into Bulgarian by two independent translators. To ensure linguistic and conceptual accuracy, the translations were subsequently reviewed and validated by two academic experts.

2. Verification of ATC codes and market availability

Each 7-digit Anatomical Therapeutic Chemical (ATC) code included in the translated EU(7)-PIM List corresponds to the fifth level of the ATC classification system, thereby identifying a single chemical substance or international nonproprietary name (INN). Accordingly, each INN was systematically reviewed to verify both the registration status and market availability of the corresponding ATC code within Bulgaria. This verification process employed two authoritative data sources: (1) the Bulgarian Drug Agency (BDA) List of Authorized Medicinal Products and (2) the National Council on Pricing and Reimbursement (NCPR) annexes and lists, which encompass both reimbursed medicines and prescription and OTC medicines outside the reimbursement system. These sources were utilized to ascertain the authorization status of each INN in the national pharmaceutical market. All ATC codes and INNs identified as unavailable on the Bulgarian market, as well as those excluded during the verification process, are presented in full in tables in Suppl. materials 1, 2.

3. Development of a digital, interoperable PIM list

A digitalization strategy was developed to facilitate the future integration of the adapted EU(7)-PIM List into Bulgarian health information systems. The list was formatted in an accessible, interoperable Excel file, specifically structured to enable subsequent conversion into a digital

database. This format was designed to provide software developers with the necessary information for digitalization and to allow future linkage with the NCPR annexes and lists, thereby supporting automated updates and the implementation of clinical decision support functionalities.

Results

The adaptation of the EU(7)-PIM List was completed following the three-stage workflow presented in Fig. 1. The bilingual translation process showed a high degree of concordance between the two independent translators, with minor discrepancies resolved through expert review. The final Bulgarian version retains all structural elements of the original EU(7)-PIM dataset. Each variable (ATC code, INN, rationale for PIM classification, warnings, dose considerations, and alternative therapies) was formatted into a standardized Excel dataset to facilitate interoperability.

Of the 277 INNs screened against the BDA and NCPR registries, 138 (49.8%) were identified as available on the Bulgarian market, whereas 139 (50.2%) were not. The largest groups of unavailable substances belonged to psycholeptics (N05), antihistamines for systemic use (R06A), and antidepressants (N06A). Several cardiovascular and metabolic sub-

groups also demonstrated notable gaps in market availability. A full breakdown of unavailable therapeutic classes and individual INNs is provided in Suppl. materials 1, 2.

A technical specification was developed to support the digital integration of the adapted list into the national health information infrastructure. As shown in Fig. 2, the system architecture incorporates dual ATC- and INN-based matching pathways, automated validity checks, and synchronization mechanisms for linkage with NCPR registries. A conceptual web-based interface was designed to allow pharmacists to perform real-time searches by INN, ATC code, or trade name and to access PIM classification rationale, warnings, dose-adjustment notes, and alternative therapies. The digital structure and related validation framework ensure interoperability, traceability, and readiness for integration with existing pharmaceutical software systems.

Discussion

The present study provides the first systematic adaptation, description of digitalization steps, and technical integration framework for implementing the EU(7)-PIM List within the Bulgarian healthcare and regulatory environment. To the best of our knowledge, no European country has yet implemented a fully digitalized version of the EU(7)-PIM List, underscoring the novelty and potential impact of the platform proposed in this study.

The translation process demonstrated high conceptual fidelity, aligning with prior research emphasizing the importance of linguistic and structural accuracy in the localization of PIM criteria for older adults. The subsequent evaluation of medicinal product availability revealed that nearly half of the INNs included in the EU(7)-PIM List are not currently marketed in Bulgaria. This finding is broadly consistent with previous cross-national comparisons demonstrating variability in PIM INN availability across Europe (Tommelein et al. 2015; Fialová et al. 2019).

Moreover, differences in national formularies, reimbursement policies, and prescribing traditions have long been recognized as determinants of PIM prevalence across European Union countries. For instance, large-scale studies have demonstrated considerable variation in PIM prescribing between Western, Central, and Eastern European regions, confirming the need for country-specific adaptation of international PIM tools (Gallagher et al. 2011).

A central outcome of this work was the development of a technical requirements specification designed to operationalize the EU(7)-PIM List within national digital infrastructures. The specification introduces a dual strategy for data linkage—via ATC codes for prescription-only medicines and INNs for OTC products—which reflects established pharmacological classification principles and mirrors approaches used in other digital medication-safety tools (O'Connor et al. 2012). Comparable national adaptations have been implemented in several other countries. Germany developed the PRISCUS list, France established the Laroche list, and the United States maintains the Beers Criteria, all of which have demonstrated clinical value and

Figure 1. Workflow for the adaptation and digitalization of the EU(7)-PIM List for the Bulgarian healthcare system.

Figure 2. System architecture and data displayed on the web platform.

have been partially integrated into electronic prescribing systems (Laroche et al. 2007; Holt et al. 2010; AGS Beers Criteria Expert Panel 2019). These examples illustrate a broader international movement toward embedding PIM criteria within digital clinical workflows.

Importantly, the preferred integration pathway identified in this study involves establishing a direct database connection with the NCPR. Such a connection is expected to enable real-time synchronization with national medicinal product repositories, a feature recognized as essential for maintaining the validity of digital prescribing tools in fast-changing pharmaceutical markets.

The system architecture incorporates automated validation algorithms to detect missing or outdated identifiers; similar mechanisms have proven effective in improving data integrity in international medication surveillance systems (Hazell and Shakir 2006). Automated validation and data reconciliation are increasingly viewed as core components of safe digital medication systems, reducing both false alerts and missed alerts in clinical decision support applications (Bates et al. 2003; van der Sijs et al. 2006).

In addition, the conceptual web-based platform developed in this study has the potential to transform the EU(7)-PIM List from a static reference table into a dynamic clinical decision support resource. Evidence from comparable tools, such as the application of Beers Criteria or STOPP/START rules within electronic health records, demonstrates that automated PIM identification significantly improves medication appropriateness and reduces adverse drug events in older adults (Huibers et al.

2019; Curtin et al. 2020; Sallevelt et al. 2022). International studies further show that integration of PIM tools within pharmacy or physician software improves deprescribing rates, supports medication reviews, and enhances interdisciplinary communication, emphasizing the importance of digital implementation (Spinewine et al. 2007).

By allowing pharmacists to query medicinal products by ATC code, INN, or trade name, and by immediately presenting the rationale for PIM classification alongside recommended alternatives, the platform aligns with international best practices for user-centered decision support design (Sligo et al. 2017). Furthermore, interoperability with existing pharmaceutical IT systems is an essential determinant of successful clinical decision support adoption, as highlighted in health informatics research demonstrating that systems embedded into routine workflows show the greatest clinical impact (Coloma et al. 2013).

The system described in this study will be further developed in accordance with the presented technical requirements as part of Work Package 3 (WP3), implemented by Research Group 3.1.3 of the ACCOMPLISH initiative (Access to Modern, Personalized, Value-based, Efficient and Sustainable Health and Pharmaceutical Services in Bulgaria); see the project № BG-RRP-2.004-0004-C01, financed by the European Union—NextGenerationEU, through the National Recovery and Resilience Plan of the Republic of Bulgaria. The digital platform outlined here therefore represents not only an independent contribution to the national medication-safety infrastructure but also a foundational component for achieving the scientific

objectives of the ACCOMPLISH program, supporting the long-term vision for personalized, sustainable, and value-based pharmaceutical care in Bulgaria.

Conclusion

This study presents the steps and actions undertaken to adapt and digitally integrate the EU(7)-PIM List into the Bulgarian healthcare system. Through rigorous linguistic validation, systematic verification against national medicinal product registries, and the development of a detailed technical integration framework, the work ensures that the PIM criteria are both contextually relevant and interoperable within national digital infrastructures. The finding that nearly half of the EU(7)-PIM substances are not available on the Bulgarian market underscores the need for country-specific availability assessments to support accurate and meaningful clinical decision support.

The introduction of a dual ATC/INN data linkage strategy, automated validation mechanisms, and provisions for real-time synchronization with regulatory databases establishes the technological basis for Bulgaria's first nationally integrated PIM identification platform. By converting the EU(7)-PIM List from a static reference into an interactive, pharmacist-focused digital tool, the proposed system aligns with international best practices and reflects successful implementations in other healthcare systems. Overall, this study advances the national infrastructure for medication safety, supports evidence-based prescribing in older adults, and contributes to broader European efforts to improve the quality, safety, and appropriateness of pharmacotherapy for aging populations.

Additional information

Conflict of interest

The authors declare that they have no conflict of interest to disclose.

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Ethical statements

The authors declared that no clinical trials were used in the present study.

The authors declared that no experiments on humans or human tissues were performed for the present study.

The authors declared that no informed consent was obtained from the humans, donors or donors' representatives participating in the study.

The authors declared that no experiments on animals were performed for the present study.

The authors declared that no commercially available immortalised human and animal cell lines were used in the present study.

Use of AI

No use of AI was reported.

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Author contributions

Both authors jointly designed the study, performed the verification of translation and adaptation of the EU(7)-PIM List, analyzed market availability data, developed the digital integration concept, and prepared and reviewed the manuscript.

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Data availability

All of the data that support the findings of this study are available in the main text or Supplementary Information.

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Supplementary material 1

ATC therapeutic groups of INNs not available in Bulgaria

Authors: Petya Milushewa, Guenka Petrova

Data type: pdf

Explanation note: This file presents a summary of ATC therapeutic subgroups from the EU(7)-PIM List for which one or more INNs were identified as not available on the Bulgarian market.

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Link: <https://doi.org/10.3897/pharmacia.73.e178435.suppl1>

Supplementary material 2

Complete PIMs from the EU(7)-PIM List not available on the Bulgarian market

Authors: Petya Milushewa, Guenka Petrova

Data type: pdf

Explanation note: This file provides a full enumeration of all individual INNs from the EU(7)-PIM List that were confirmed as not marketed in Bulgaria.

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